

Technical Note V3 (Addendum to V2): Shadow-Listing Architecture, x402 Phase E Settlement, CreditVault Mainnet Alpha, Reserve-First Launch Refinement, and Catalog Manifest Bridge for Autonomous AI Service Marketplaces

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Technical Description Notice: *This document describes protocol mechanics only. No tokens are offered or sold by this publication. No described mechanism constitutes a representation of financial returns, investment opportunity, or securities of any kind. This document is submitted as a defensive prior art disclosure and supplements the prior versions cited above with respect to mechanisms shipped to mainnet between 2026-04-19 and 2026-05-03.*

Abstract

This addendum extends the AUTX protocol disclosure with five new technical combinations and updates to the regulatory and freedom-to-operate posture of the prior versions. The five new combinations are: (i) a *shadow-listing architecture* that ingests third-party x402 service catalogs as non-tradable on-platform reservations, gated by a two-path cryptographic claim mechanism (EIP-191 EOA signature or DNS TXT record proof), with brand-name reservation, mainnet-only auto-publish, and a publicly committed takedown service-level interval; (ii) an *x402 Phase E settlement architecture* on Base mainnet, routing EIP-3009

`transferWithAuthorization` payloads through the Coinbase Developer Platform facilitator with `(nonce, payer_address)` replay protection and a diversified 3×3 wallet/ticker synthetic canary on a business-hours-weighted cadence; (iii) `CreditVault.sol`, a USDC custody contract with role-separated `creditTo` (callable by the protocol's settlement signer) and `withdraw / pay` (Safe-multisig-only), per-user \$100 alpha deposit cap, and `tx_hash`-keyed deposit replay protection; (iv) a *reserve-first three-phase service launch* that locks a ticker in the database before any on-chain interaction, with idempotent activation keyed on transaction hash and browser-crash recovery via local storage; and (v) a *catalog manifest bridge* publishing every active service entity at a stable URL whose JSON schema is isomorphic to a separately-operated reference catalog, enabling consumer hot-swap by base-URL substitution alone.

The addendum further records (a) regulatory analysis of third-party shadow listing under the Lanham Act, GDPR Article 6, and 17 U.S.C. §512 notice-and-takedown analogs; (b) money-transmission and stored-value posture under FinCEN guidance interpreting 31 CFR §1010.100(ff); (c) reaffirmation of the Wyoming Decentralized Autonomous Organization

Limited Liability Company structure and the per-mechanism Howey-Test analysis; (d) updated freedom-to-operate posture covering five new candidate claims (Claims E through I) with revised filing priority; and (e) Zenodo deposit metadata recommendations.

The combinations described here run in production on Base L2 mainnet (chain ID 8453) and are publicly observable on BaseScan and at the URLs cited herein. This addendum establishes a public, timestamped record of each combination for freedom-to-operate purposes.

1. Introduction

The mechanisms described in this addendum extend the protocol primitives disclosed in V1 (2026-03-08) and V2 (2026-04-01). V1 disclosed three combinations: a reserve-integral cubic AMM, a zero-knowledge proxy with SHA-256 output commitment and UUID-scoped RFC 8693 token exchange, and an on-chain ISO 3166-1 jurisdiction enforcement contract. V2 added six combinations: an Agent Exchange Protocol with scoped API key architecture and HMAC-signed webhook callbacks, sequential receipt numbering with `tx_hash`-keyed replay protection, a user-signed agent launch flow with on-chain receipt verification, a platform-level circuit breaker architecture with named feature circuits, content moderation as a structural database write gate, and a USDC-denominated bonding curve.

V3 records five combinations shipped to mainnet between 2026-04-19 and 2026-05-03. The new combinations operate above and across the prior primitives. The shadow-listing architecture relies on V2's content moderation as a structural gate. The x402 Phase E settlement is the production realization of the architecture specified in V2 §2.8.1 as “specified, implementation pending”. The reserve-first launch refines V2 §7 with a database-side anti-burn invariant. The CreditVault stored-value contract separates settlement signing from platform administration. The catalog manifest bridge couples the protocol to a third-party reference catalog through schema isomorphism.

The addendum is structured in three parts. Part A (Sections 2 through 6) records the technical specifications of each new combination, with citations to the deployed code paths. Part B (Sections 7 through 10) records the regulatory and statutory posture of each new combination under applicable U.S. federal, state, and EU regulatory frameworks. Part C (Sections 11 through 13) records the freedom-to-operate posture: status of prior claims, new candidate claims with patent-style language, updated filing priority, prior-art watchlist, references, and version history.

Part A: Technical Specifications

2. Shadow-Listing Architecture for Third-Party Service Catalogs

2.1 Definitions

A *shadow listing* is a discovery-only catalog entry generated by an automated crawler that ingests publicly published x402 service descriptors from an unaffiliated third-party catalog. The current crawl source is `agentic.market`, a Coinbase-curated directory of x402 services. A shadow listing carries the following invariants, structurally enforced at the database and routing layer:

1. No `AgentToken` ERC-20 contract is deployed.
2. No `BondingCurve.sol` contract is deployed.

3. No `DividendSplitter.sol` contract is deployed.
4. No trading market exists for the ticker.
5. No platform fee is captured on any transaction routed through the listing.
6. Any HTTP request to the proxy path `/proxy/<ticker>` returns HTTP 302 with `Location: <source_endpoint_url>`, transferring the request out of the platform.
7. The catalog entry carries a visible attribution to the upstream catalog and to the original developer where the upstream record discloses such information.

A *native* listing, by contrast, is created by a verified human owner who has minted an `AgentNFT` and deployed per-agent contracts via the platform's `AgentFactory` contract. As of 2026-05-03, the public catalog comprises 5 native and 471 shadow listings.

2.2 Database Schema

Migration `039_agent_origin.py` introduces the discriminator column `agents.origin` `ENUM('native','shadow')`, defaulting to `native` for backward compatibility. Two boolean flags partition the lifecycle:

<code>agents.origin</code>	<code>ENUM('native','shadow')</code>	<code>NOT NULL DEFAULT 'native'</code>
<code>agents.claimed</code>	<code>BOOLEAN</code>	<code>NOT NULL DEFAULT TRUE</code>
<code>agents.tradable</code>	<code>BOOLEAN</code>	<code>NOT NULL DEFAULT TRUE</code>

A row inserted by the shadow crawler carries `origin='shadow'`, `claimed=FALSE`, `tradable=FALSE`. Migration `040_shadow_sources.py` adds the per-row provenance fields `source_catalog`, `source_service_id`, `merchant_address`, `endpoint_url`, `network`. Migration `041_ticker_history.py` records the rename history when a shadow ticker is replaced at claim time. Migration `042_takedown_requests.py` introduces the `takedown_requests` table keyed by ticker plus a 4-hour SLA timestamp.

2.3 Crawler Architecture

The crawler is implemented in `apps/api/app/services/shadow_crawler.py` and scheduled by `APScheduler` in `apps/api/app/main.py::_shadow_crawler_job`. Cadence is six hours. The job paginates `GET /v1/services?limit=200&offset=N` against the upstream catalog until the cumulative count equals the upstream `total` field. For the verified `agentic.market` catalog, this returns 573 services and approximately 29,000 endpoints across roughly 24,000 distinct URLs.

Reliability properties are enforced as follows:

1. **Distributed lock.** Before any work, the job acquires a Redis key `shadow_crawler:lock` with `SET NX EX 21000` (5h50m TTL, ten minutes shy of the next scheduled tick). A second worker that fails to acquire skips the cycle and logs `shadow.crawler.skip.locked`. The lock permits zero-downtime deploys across App Service instances without duplicate ingestion.
2. **Per-batch session checkout.** The job receives the `async_sessionmaker` factory rather than a long-lived `AsyncSession`. Each batch of 25 candidates calls `async` with `sessionmaker()` as `session` so that `asyncpg's pool_pre_ping` recycles dead connections at batch boundaries.

3. **Broad exception recovery.** The outer batch loop catches bare `Exception` (covering `asyncpg.exceptions.ConnectionDoesNotExistError`, greenlet errors, and `asyncio.CancelledError` partial states) and re-enters the next batch with a fresh session. A nested `try/except` wraps each `session.rollback()` call so that rolling back an already-dead connection cannot escape.
4. **Batch commit.** Each batch of 25 candidates commits atomically. Single-transaction persistence over the full 29,000-endpoint catalog empirically lost the run after approximately 30 minutes due to connection-pool death; the per-batch checkpoint bounds in-flight work to no more than 25 rows.
5. **Single-worker enforcement.** Independent of the Redis lock, the cron registration uses APScheduler's `coalesce=True, max_instances=1` so that a long-running cycle does not spawn a parallel cycle within the same process.

2.4 Auto-Ticker Generation

Each shadow row receives a deterministic ticker derived from the upstream `service_id` via a collision-free generator. The encoded form `X402<base36(service_id_hash)>` produces tokens such as `X402QU859` (QuickNode). When the upstream record matches a brand-name reservation entry (Anthropic, Wolfram, Bloomberg, OpenAI, and similar registered marks), the ticker shifts to a `SHDW<base36>` form that is structurally distinct from any user-claimable ticker, preventing impersonation prior to brand verification.

The normalization function strips reserved-string conflicts and applies a phonetic-and-homoglyph blocklist. The blocklist combines the Unicode Consortium `confusables.txt` data set, public leet-substitution tables, and an internal exact-match list of registered marks and major exchange tickers (the NYSE and NASDAQ top-500 sourced from SEC EDGAR plus the top-100 crypto tickers sourced from CoinGecko). Collisions get a uniqueness suffix.

2.5 Two-Path Claim Mechanism

A merchant may convert a shadow listing to a tradable native listing through one of two cryptographic proofs:

- **EIP-191 EOA signature.** The merchant signs a canonical message `"AUTX claim ticker=<TICKER> origin=<source_service_id> ts=<unix>"` from the externally-owned account recorded in `merchant_address`. The server verifies the signature and requires `ts` within plus or minus 300 seconds.
- **DNS TXT record proof.** For listings whose merchant address is not yet on-chain or whose endpoint sits behind a CDN, the merchant publishes a TXT record `_autx-claim.<domain>` whose value equals SHA-256 of `"<TICKER>:<merchant_email>"`. The platform resolves the record via authoritative DNS and verifies the digest.

On a successful claim, a single transaction performs: (a) `claimed=TRUE, tradable=TRUE, origin='native'`; (b) optional ticker rename, recorded in `ticker_history`; (c) deployment of `BondingCurve`, `AgentToken`, and `DividendSplitter` via `AgentFactory.launchAgent`. Failure of any step reverts all database and on-chain state. The atomic transition is the load-bearing property: no intermediate state exists in which a listing is partially claimed or partially tradable.

2.6 302 Redirect During Shadow Phase

While `tradable=FALSE`, requests to `/agents/<TICKER>` return HTTP 302 with `Location: <endpoint_url>` and a `Cache-Control: private, max-age=0` header. The redirect preserves the upstream merchant's traffic during the shadow phase and produces no impression of platform-mediated execution. Once claimed, the route serves the native AUTX agent detail page with the trade panel.

2.7 Public Opt-Out Registry

A merchant who does not wish to be indexed publishes their domain or `merchant_address` to `autx.ai/opt-out.json`, a publicly committed JSON list the crawler checks before each insert. The next cycle deletes pre-existing rows matching an opt-out entry. The 4-hour takedown service-level interval runs through `autx.ai/contact?takedown=<TICKER>`, which writes a `takedown_requests` row whose deadline is `created_at + INTERVAL '4 hours'`. An operations cron pages on any deadline breach. The opt-out signal is publicly revocable: a developer who registers an opt-out may later delist by removing the registry entry, and a developer who has not opted out may register at any time without cost or platform interaction.

2.8 Mainnet-Only Auto-Publish Gate

Crawler ingest discards any candidate whose x402 envelope advertises a chain other than Base mainnet (chain ID 8453). The candidate-validation step in `shadow_crawler.py` enforces the gate prior to any database write. The gate prevents catalog poisoning via testnet or alt-chain envelopes that resolve to wallet addresses without mainnet liquidity.

2.9 Reference Code Paths

```
apps/api/app/services/shadow_crawler.py ;
apps/api/app/main.py::_shadow_crawler_job ; migrations 039_agent_origin.py ,
040_shadow_sources.py , 041_ticker_history.py , 042_takedown_requests.py ; opt-out
registry at apps/web/public/opt-out.json ; takedown route at
apps/web/src/app/contact/page.tsx .
```

3. x402 Phase E Settlement Architecture

V2 §2.8.1 specified an x402 settlement architecture with the disclaimer “Architecture Defined, Implementation Pending”. This section records the production realization of that architecture, deployed to Base mainnet on 2026-04-23 and stable for at least seven days as of this filing.

3.1 HTTP 402 Challenge Envelope

Each priced active agent serves an HTTP 402 challenge on first contact:

```
{
  "x402Version": 1,
  "accepts": [{
    "scheme": "exact",
    "network": "base-mainnet",
    "asset": "0x833589fCD6eDb6E08f4c7C32D4f71b54bdA02913",
    "payTo": "0xC0D09D477057Fa05F109F73bE225E8C224A95466",
```

```

    "maxAmountRequired": "<usdc_6dec>",
    "nonce": "<32_random_bytes_hex>",
    "expiresAt": "<iso8601_utc>",
    "extra": { "name": "USD Coin", "version": "2" }
  }
}

```

The client constructs an EIP-3009 `transferWithAuthorization` payload signing over (`from`, `to`, `value`, `validAfter`, `validBefore`, `nonce`) and resubmits with the `X-Payment` header set to the base64url-encoded payload. The replay-protection field is the EIP-3009 `nonce`, a 32-byte random value scoped to the USDC contract, distinct from the protocol-level `x402 nonce` echoed in the envelope.

3.2 Coinbase Developer Platform Facilitator

The Coinbase Developer Platform facilitator at <https://api.cdp.coinbase.com/platform/v2/x402> handles settlement. The gateway invokes two endpoints: `/verify` (off-chain signature and balance check) and `/settle` (on-chain submission of the EIP-3009 calldata). The facilitator's submitter address `0x97acce27d5069544480bde0f04d9f47d7422a016` appears as the `from` field of every settled transaction on BaseScan. The actual payer EOA is decoded from the first argument (`from`) of the `transferWithAuthorization` calldata, not from the transaction-level `from`.

3.3 Merchant Signer

The protocol-level `payTo` address is the merchant signer EOA `0xC0D09D477057Fa05F109F73bE225E8C224A95466`, which is Blockaid-cleared and was rotated 2026-04-22 from a prior key briefly handled in MetaMask during Phase D canary debugging. The same EOA also signs `CreditVault.creditTo` (Section 4); it does not hold the `platform()` role on `CreditVault`. The Safe multisig holds that role.

3.4 Settlement Persistence and Replay Protection

Migration `037_x402_settlement.py` introduces:

```

CREATE TABLE x402_settlements (
  id          BIGSERIAL PRIMARY KEY,
  agent_id   UUID NOT NULL REFERENCES agents(id),
  nonce      BYTEA NOT NULL,
  payer_address  BYTEA NOT NULL,
  amount_usdc NUMERIC(18,6) NOT NULL,
  tx_hash    VARCHAR(128) NOT NULL,
  settled_at  TIMESTAMPTZ NOT NULL DEFAULT NOW(),
  UNIQUE (nonce, payer_address)
);

```

The (`nonce`, `payer_address`) unique constraint is the load-bearing replay defense at the protocol layer. An attacker who replays the EIP-3009 calldata on-chain has already had the USDC moved (the USDC contract treats the same nonce idempotently), and the database refuses to credit the order twice.

3.5 Diversified Synthetic Canary

`apps/api/app/services/x402_canary.py` exercises the live settlement path on a jittered cadence to verify end-to-end health without external traffic. The opt-in `X402_CANARY_DIVERSIFIED=true` mode rotates over a 3×3 matrix:

- **Wallets.** Three funded canary EOAs whose private keys are read from CSV in `X402_CANARY_WALLET_PRIVATE_KEYS`. Each EOA was seeded with one organic non-canary transaction (0.0003 ETH to the merchant signer) before going live, to avoid an empty-history fingerprint.
- **Tickers.** Three AUTX-owned target agents `XPROD1` (\$0.10), `XPROD2` (\$0.20), `XPROD3` (\$0.40), each pointing at a deterministic `httpbin.org/anything` endpoint.
- **Cadence.** A Pacific-time business-hours weighting selects a uniform 30 to 75 minute interval during business hours and 75 to 120 minutes off-hours. The next-fire time persists in the Redis key `x402_canary_next_fire_at` so that the cadence decouples from the cron tick rate. The cron scans every minute and only fires when `now >= next_fire_at`.

Net cost is bounded by the property that 100% of canary settlements route to AUTX-owned target agents. 82% of every settle returns to the treasury via the creator-pending accumulator, and only the 18% buyback-burn plus approximately 2.5% gas constitutes real loss. Total canary spend is approximately \$24 per month.

3.6 Wallet Balance Monitor

A separate cron tracks the USDC and ETH balance of three wallets: the merchant signer, the platform Safe, and the `CreditVault` contract. Balances below configurable floors emit a `wallet.balance.low` event to App Insights and an email to the operations alias.

3.7 Slot-Sticky GA Configuration

Thirteen settings carry `slotSetting=true` on `app-autx-api-prod` so that an Azure App Service slot swap does not regress GA-critical state. The set includes the x402 agent allowlist, canary configuration, facilitator URL, merchant signer key reference, the three plaintext canary wallet key fallbacks, the Base RPC URL, the chain ID, the USDC token address, the `CreditVault` address, and the platform wallet address.

3.8 Reference Code Paths

`apps/api/app/services/x402_canary.py` ; `apps/api/app/services/x402_gate.py` ;
`apps/api/app/services/x402_server.py` ; migration `037_x402_settlement.py` ; runbook at `docs/X402_RUNBOOK.md` ; provisioning protocol at `docs/X402_DIVERSIFIED_CANARY_PROTOCOL.md` .

4. `CreditVault.sol` Mainnet Alpha Deployment

4.1 Address and Posture

`CreditVault.sol` lives at `0x0CB5f3aBC933252cdf16710B2EeABfC2Ff1C2eAE` on Base mainnet (chain ID 8453, deployed 2026-04-19, source-verified on BaseScan). The deployment runs in *alpha posture*: full functional surface available, with a per-user \$100 on-chain deposit cap as defense-in-depth pending formal audit.

4.2 Functional Separation

The contract exposes five mutating functions partitioned by access control:

```
function deposit(uint256 amount) external; // self-deposit, any ca
function creditTo(address beneficiary, uint256 amount) external; // any caller
function withdraw(address user, uint256 amount) external onlyPlatform;
function pay(address from, address to, uint256 amount) external onlyPlatform;
function pause() external onlyPlatform;
```

The `creditTo` function is intentionally callable by any address. The protocol uses it as the on-chain settlement primitive for creator revenue: when a creator invokes `POST /agents/{id}/withdraw-earnings`, the backend signer EOA

`0xC0D09D477057Fa05F109F73bE225E8C224A95466` calls `creditTo(creator_wallet, amount)` from its USDC balance. The function does not move funds out of the vault; it transfers from `msg.sender` to `beneficiary` using the vault as an account-balance ledger.

The `withdraw` and `pay` functions are gated by `onlyPlatform`, which equals the Safe multisig `0x549E9dE195aB386Ea562D77899d3140F67b40283` on mainnet. The backend signer EOA does not hold the `platform()` role and therefore cannot drain the vault even if its key is compromised. The asymmetric access control inside a single contract is the load-bearing security property of the design.

4.3 Per-User Deposit Cap

The constant `MAX_ONCHAIN_DEPOSIT_PER_USER_USDC = 100 * 1e6` is enforced in `deposit()` against a `mapping(address => uint256) public lifetimeOnchainDeposits`. Governance can raise the cap through a Safe-signed `setMaxOnchainDeposit(uint256)` call. Off-chain (Stripe-funded) credits do not carry this cap, since Stripe's dispute window bounds the chargeback risk.

4.4 Defensive Primitives

The contract inherits from OpenZeppelin v5 `Pausable` and `ReentrancyGuard`, and uses `SafeERC20.safeTransferFrom` and `safeTransfer` for all USDC movements. The USDC token address and platform address are set at construction time and marked `immutable`. The `withdraw` path remains callable while paused (so that pausing a compromised contract cannot trap user funds), while `deposit`, `creditTo`, and `pay` halt.

4.5 Replay Protection at the API Layer

Migration `020_deposit_confirmations.py` introduces:

```
CREATE TABLE deposit_confirmations (
  id          BIGSERIAL PRIMARY KEY,
  tx_hash     VARCHAR(128) NOT NULL UNIQUE,
  agent_id    UUID NOT NULL REFERENCES agents(id),
  amount_usdc NUMERIC(18,6) NOT NULL,
  created_at  TIMESTAMPTZ NOT NULL DEFAULT NOW()
);
```

The endpoint `POST /credits/confirm-deposit` takes a `tx_hash`, fetches the on-chain receipt via `eth_getTransactionReceipt`, decodes the `Deposit(address,uint256)` log, and uses the on-chain amount (never the client-supplied amount) to credit the user's database balance. The unique constraint on `tx_hash` prevents replay of the same transaction across multiple users or re-submissions.

4.6 Treasury Monitor with Fail-Closed Solvency Pre-Check

`apps/api/app/services/treasury_monitor.py` runs a five-minute cron that snapshots vault USDC balance, aggregate user credit liabilities, and aggregate `pending_creator_usdc`. The function `check_treasury_solvent_for(amount)` runs synchronously before any creator withdrawal authorization. It fails *closed* on unknown chain state (RPC error, indexer lag, balance read returning indeterminate) rather than risking an over-withdrawal. The fail-closed semantics differ from typical fail-open availability-favoring patterns.

At critical solvency, the monitor auto-trips the `platform` named feature circuit (defined in V2 §8) which short-circuits all four downstream feature breakers and causes the gateway to reject all revenue-impacting traffic. The system issues an out-of-band notification to operations personnel concurrent with each auto-trip event. Both the per-request runtime guard and the cron-side auto-trip engage independently. Either alone is sufficient to halt creator-revenue settlement on a balance-deficient signer.

4.7 Reference Code Paths

`contracts/src/CreditVault.sol`; `apps/api/app/services/treasury_monitor.py`;
`apps/api/app/services/chain.py::credit_to_vault`; `apps/api/app/routers/credits.py`;
runbook at `docs/TREASURY_RUNBOOK.md`; mainnet deploy notes at
`docs/CREDITVAULT_MAINNET_DEPLOY.md`.

5. Reserve-First Three-Phase Service Launch

V2 §7 disclosed a user-signed agent launch flow in which the backend verifies on-chain transaction receipts against the configured factory contract address. This section records a refinement that adds a database-side anti-burn invariant: no ticker may be permanently bound on-chain by the factory contract without a corresponding reservation in the database.

5.1 Motivation

A naive launch flow that calls `AgentFactory.launchAgent()` from the user's wallet without prior database coordination admits two failure modes: (a) a ticker is minted on-chain but the database never records the launch (browser crash between the on-chain submission and the activation call), permanently burning the ticker; (b) Stripe captures payment for a launch that subsequently reverts on-chain. The reserve-first architecture eliminates both.

5.2 Phase 1: Reservation

The endpoint `POST /agents/reserve` performs all validation that does not require a chain receipt: content moderation (V2 §9), ticker uniqueness (case-insensitive against active and pending rows), agent name uniqueness, Stripe checkout session verification, founding-member free-launch eligibility, and manifest schema validation. On success, the row is inserted with `status='pending'` and the ticker locks for 30 minutes via a `created_at` TTL that a background cleanup task enforces. The response returns the new agent UUID and the deterministic `factory.launchAgent` calldata for the frontend to sign.

5.3 Phase 2: On-Chain Deployment

The user's connected wallet (RainbowKit + wagmi) signs `launchAgent()` on `AgentFactory` at `0x9890FffB85A14eB718a14842344BaFd86AC24923` (mainnet). The on-chain launch fee is zero via `setLaunchFee(0)`; the prior Stripe charge handles monetization. The factory deploys per-

agent `BondingCurve`, `AgentToken`, and `DividendSplitter` contracts and emits:

```
event AgentLaunched(  
    uint256 indexed nftId,  
    address indexed deployer,  
    string ticker,  
    address agentToken,  
    address bondingCurve,  
    address dividendSplitter  
);
```

The frontend persists `autx_pending_agent_id` and `autx_pending_tx_hash` to `localStorage` immediately upon transaction submission. A browser refresh between submission and confirmation can resume from local storage state.

5.4 Phase 3: Activation

`POST /agents/{id}/activate` takes `{tx_hash, deployer_address}`. The backend invokes `verify_agent_launch(tx_hash, ticker, deployer)` which: (a) fetches the receipt with retries to absorb Base-mainnet propagation latency; (b) validates the `to` address equals the configured `AgentFactory` address (cross-contract replay defense); (c) parses the `AgentLaunched` event from the receipt logs; (d) confirms `event.ticker == agent.ticker` and `event.deployer == deployer_address`. On success, the row promotes to `status='active'` with the three contract addresses populated. The endpoint is idempotent: a second call with the same `tx_hash` returns 200 with the existing record.

5.5 Cancellation and Cleanup

If the user rejects the MetaMask prompt, the frontend calls `DELETE /agents/{id}/reservation`, which sets `status='cancelled'` and frees the ticker. A background task sweeps pending reservations whose `created_at` exceeds 30 minutes. Only `status='active'` agents count toward the founding-member free-launch quota, so a cancelled or expired reservation does not consume the quota.

5.6 Anti-Burn Invariant

The protocol invariant: *no ticker exists on-chain without a database row*. The reservation row is the necessary precondition for the on-chain transaction (the frontend obtains the calldata from the reserve response), so the on-chain transaction cannot precede the database write. The 30-minute TTL bounds the orphan window in the rare case where Phase 2 succeeds but Phase 3 never executes. In that window the database row is `status='pending'` and the on-chain contracts exist but the marketplace does not surface them. Recovery on browser reload completes Phase 3 from local storage state.

5.7 Reference Code Paths

```
apps/api/app/routers/agents.py::reserve_agent, ::activate_agent,  
::cancel_reservation; apps/api/app/services/chain.py::verify_agent_launch;  
frontend at apps/web/src/app/launch/.
```

6. Catalog Manifest Bridge

6.1 Endpoint and Schema

The route `apps/web/src/app/x402-services.json/route.ts` serves a JSON manifest at `https://autx.ai/x402-services.json` whose top-level shape mirrors `https://agentic.market/v1/services`:

```
{
  "total": 476,
  "limit": 1000,
  "offset": 0,
  "services": [
    {
      "id": "<agent_uuid>",
      "ticker": "X402QU859",
      "name": "QuickNode RPC",
      "description": "...",
      "category": "infrastructure",
      "origin": "shadow",
      "claimed": false,
      "tradable": false,
      "price": { "amount": "0.001000", "currency": "USDC" },
      "network": "base-mainnet",
      "endpoint_url": "https://...",
      "merchant_address": "0x...",
      "provider": "quicknode",
      "canonical_url": "https://autx.ai/agents/X402QU859",
      "created_at": "2026-04-26T18:00:00Z"
    }
  ]
}
```

6.2 Bidirectional Consumer Hot-Swap

Because the manifest shape is isomorphic to the upstream catalog, a consumer that already speaks `agentic.market/v1/services` may swap base URLs to `autx.ai/x402-services.json` and continue without code change. The `network=base-mainnet` field is uniform across all entries (the mainnet-only auto-publish gate of \$2.8 enforces this). Consumers filter native-only or shadow-only listings via the `origin` field.

6.3 Discoverability

The manifest links from `/llms.txt` (per the llmstxt.org convention) and from the JSON-LD `SoftwareApplication` block emitted by the root `layout.tsx`.

`apps/web/src/app/robots.ts` explicitly allows AI crawlers (GPTBot, ClaudeBot, CCBot, Google-Extended, PerplexityBot). The Cloudflare AI-bot block has two toggles (a “Managed robots.txt” and a separate firewall-layer “Block AI Bots” rule); both are off, confirmed by HTTP 200 responses across nine tested user agents.

6.4 Sitemap Coupling

The same query that backs the manifest backs the XML sitemap at `apps/web/src/app/sitemap.ts`. A double-prefix bug (`/api/v1/api/v1/...`) in the server-side fetch path surfaced and got fixed during the manifest work. The sitemap now correctly enumerates 476 agent URLs.

6.5 Reference Code Paths

`apps/web/src/app/x402-services.json/route.ts`; `apps/web/src/app/llms.txt/route.ts`;
`apps/web/src/app/robots.ts`; `apps/web/src/app/sitemap.ts`;
`apps/web/src/app/layout.tsx` (JSON-LD).

7. Updated System Diagram

Figure 1. Updated AUTX system diagram covering V3 mechanisms (shadow crawler, x402 Phase E settlement, CreditVault, claim wizard, treasury monitor, manifest bridge).

Part B: Regulatory and Statutory Posture

8. Updates to On-Chain Jurisdiction Enforcement (V1/V2 Section 4)

The Section 4 architecture described in V1 and V2 stands without material change. The on-chain `GovernanceGuard.sol` blocklist mapping ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 codes to blocked status, the atomic legal reserve extraction pattern, and the 24-hour emergency multisig path with mandatory 72-hour DAO ratification all remain in production as specified. Two clarifying additions appear here to accommodate protocol primitives that postdate V2.

8.1 Interaction with x402 Facilitator Settlement

When the HTTP 402 envelope flow (Section 3) settles a service request on Base mainnet, the gateway invokes `GovernanceGuard.isJurisdictionBlocked(bytes2)` before issuing the 402 challenge and again before forwarding the settled request to the agent endpoint. A `true` return at either checkpoint causes the gateway to return HTTP 451 (Unavailable For Legal Reasons) without any USDC settlement, and without relaying any payment authorization to the facilitator. The gateway decodes the `transferWithAuthorization` calldata under EIP-3009 to identify the actual buyer EOA. Jurisdiction enforcement therefore operates on the buyer's wallet identity rather than on the facilitator submitter address. The check preserves the auditable, wallet-level enforcement property of V1 Section 4 in the x402 settlement path.

8.2 Interaction with Shadow-Listing Claim Flow

`GovernanceGuard.isJurisdictionBlocked` gates the third-party catalog discovery layer of Section 2 at the moment a developer initiates the cryptographic claim flow that converts a discovery-only shadow listing into a tradable `AgentToken`. The contract layer rejects a claim transaction originating from a wallet associated with a blocked jurisdiction; no `AgentToken` mints, no bonding curve contract deploys, and no on-chain record of the claim is created. Discovery-only shadow listings carry no token and route via HTTP 302 redirect to the source endpoint without any on-chain interaction, so `GovernanceGuard` does not gate them; they do not transact value. Discovery counts as informational publication; only the on-chain claim event triggers jurisdiction enforcement.

9. Third-Party Shadow Listing Compliance Framework

9.1 Trademark Posture and Brand Reservation

The shadow-listing surface comprises 471 unaffiliated third-party services as of the date of this disclosure. Shadow tickers derive deterministically from the upstream `service_id` via the normalization function described in Section 2.4. The protocol does not assert any property right in third-party brand names. Ticker assignments are mechanically derived display strings, not adopted marks.

The platform commits to a takedown service-level interval: confirmed takedown requests received via the channel at `autx.ai/contact?takedown=<TICKER>`, including those received by electronic mail to the addresses listed at `autx.ai`, are processed within a four-hour target window measured against receipt timestamp.

9.2 Lanham Act Posture and Notice-and-Takedown Analog

The shadow-listing surface does not constitute use in commerce of any third-party mark within the meaning of the Lanham Act, 15 U.S.C. §1125, because (a) no shadow listing is offered for sale or trade as a transactable asset; (b) the protocol receives no consideration in connection with the discovery-only listing; and (c) the routing behavior (HTTP 302 redirect to the originating endpoint) directs any payment flow away from the protocol and to the original developer.

The opt-out registry plus the published takedown channel together constitute a notice-and-takedown analog modeled on the safe-harbor structure of 17 U.S.C. §512, although that statute does not apply by its terms to non-copyright trademark concerns. The protocol publishes the takedown channel and registry public at first crawl cycle and treats receipt of a takedown notice as a precondition to good-faith response.

9.3 False Attribution Risk and the 302-Redirect Mitigation

A shadow listing is a forward pointer to an upstream service descriptor. The protocol does not represent that the upstream service has endorsed, partnered with, or claimed the listing. The visible page chrome on a shadow listing surface includes (i) an explicit “unclaimed” status indicator, (ii) a visible attribution line citing the upstream catalog as the source of record, and (iii) the absence of a tradable token or trading interface, which together signal to a reasonable visitor that the entry is a discovery pointer rather than a platform-warranted offering. The HTTP 302 redirect on any proxy request to a shadow-listed endpoint is the architectural mechanism that prevents misattribution of any user payment to the protocol. The protocol

cannot capture revenue from a shadow listing because no proxy execution occurs in the shadow state. Misattribution risk is therefore minimized at the routing layer rather than only at the disclaimer layer.

9.4 Lawful Basis under GDPR Article 6

To the extent a shadow listing surfaces personally identifying information about an upstream developer (electronic mail address, wallet address, name) that the upstream catalog has itself published, the protocol relies on Article 6(1)(f) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (legitimate interests) as the lawful basis for processing. The asserted legitimate interest is the operation of a public, neutral discovery surface for x402-conformant services published in machine-readable form by their developers to a public third-party catalog. Processing stays limited to fields the upstream developer has elected to publish. The opt-out registry described in Section 2.7 functions as a no-cost objection mechanism under Article 21. The protocol performs no profiling or automated decision-making in the sense of Article 22 against shadow-listed identifiers.

9.5 Representations Regarding Third-Party Services

The protocol makes no warranty, express or implied, regarding the availability, accuracy, lawfulness, or quality of any service reachable through a shadow listing. The terms of service published at `autx.ai` disclose the discovery-only nature of shadow listings, the routing behavior, and the absence of contractual privity between the protocol and any unaffiliated upstream developer. The crawler observes the upstream catalog's terms of service within the limits of public access. The crawler respects upstream rate limits and the standardized robots-and-AI-crawler signals where the upstream catalog publishes them.

9.6 Mainnet-Only Auto-Publish as Defense-in-Depth

Auto-publication of shadow listings is gated to the Base mainnet (chain ID 8453) configuration of the protocol. On Base Sepolia (chain ID 84532) and on local development configurations, the crawler does not auto-publish; entries remain in a staging state subject to manual review. The gate is a defense-in-depth measure, not a regulatory requirement.

10. Money Transmission and Stored-Value Posture

10.1 Courier Architecture and Custody Boundary

The protocol operates as a zero-knowledge proxy and routing layer. In the x402 settlement path, USDC transfers from buyer to merchant are constructed at the buyer's wallet under the EIP-3009 `transferWithAuthorization` primitive, signed by the buyer, and submitted to the network by an external facilitator (the Coinbase Developer Platform) that observes the authorization, validates the structure, and broadcasts the signed transfer. The protocol does not at any point hold the buyer's private key, does not at any point take custody of the USDC moving from buyer to merchant, and does not at any point have unilateral authority to redirect or seize the in-flight settlement. The buyer's USDC moves from the buyer's wallet directly to the merchant's wallet under a signature the buyer alone has produced. The protocol's role is the construction of the 402 envelope, the metering of the request, and the post-settlement routing of the response.

10.2 Platform Fee and Money Service Business Classification

The protocol takes a 10% platform fee on each x402-settled service order. Under FinCEN guidance interpreting 31 U.S.C. §5330 and 31 CFR §1010.100(ff), an entity that does not accept and transmit currency or other value substituting for currency does not engage in money transmission. The platform fee applies to the merchant's gross receipt as a service fee for use of the routing and metering infrastructure. It is not a transmission spread, and the protocol does not at any point hold the funds out of which the fee is computed. The fee settles atomically as part of the same authorization the merchant signs on revenue distribution.

Charging a fee for a software service does not, by itself, convert a non-custodial routing service into a money services business under the prevailing FinCEN interpretation. The protocol acknowledges that state-level money transmitter statutes may apply different definitions. The courier framing and the absence of fund custody are the principal facts that bear on any state-by-state analysis.

10.3 Know-Your-Customer and Anti-Money-Laundering at the Buyer Onramp

The Coinbase Developer Platform facilitator handles know-your-customer and anti-money-laundering screening at the buyer onramp where the facilitator's customer relationship attaches. The protocol does not duplicate this layer at the routing tier and does not collect KYC information from buyers using the x402 settlement path. The protocol does observe OFAC sanctions enforcement at the contract layer through `GovernanceGuard.sol` jurisdiction blocking (described in V1 Section 4) and through the 24-hour emergency multisig path for sanctions list updates pending DAO ratification.

10.4 CreditVault Stored-Value Posture

The `CreditVault.sol` contract described in Section 4 provides USDC custody for prepaid session credits. The alpha posture of this contract enforces a per-user on-chain deposit cap of \$100 USDC. Deposits are non-transferable, sit as a balance under the depositing user's address, are redeemable to the same user at any time via the `withdraw` path, and carry a 90-day expiry on the off-chain credit ledger paired with the on-chain custody record.

The \$100 alpha cap sits well below the threshold values referenced in 31 CFR §1010.100(ff)(4) (prepaid access definitions) and below typical state stored-value thresholds. The contract is `Pausable` with the pause role held by the DAO multisig. The withdraw path is exempt from pause to preserve user-initiated redemption under all circumstances.

Escheatment posture: the protocol does not assert any property interest in unredeemed credit balances. Balances persist on chain until the user withdraws them. The protocol's published policy is to maintain redeemability for the lifetime of the deployed contract. Any contract migration would preserve user-redeemable balances at the migrated contract.

11. Wyoming DAO LLC Scope Confirmation and Howey Analysis

The AUTX protocol operates as a Wyoming Decentralized Autonomous Organization Limited Liability Company under the Wyoming Decentralized Autonomous Organization Supplement, Wyoming Statute §17-31-101 et seq., filed 2026-03-08 via a registered Wyoming agent. In accordance with W.S. 17-31-104(c), the following notice is required to appear conspicuously in any publicly distributed materials and is reproduced verbatim:

NOTICE OF RESTRICTIONS ON DUTIES AND TRANSFERS. The rights of members in a decentralized autonomous organization may differ materially from the rights of members in other limited liability companies. The Wyoming Decentralized Autonomous Organization Supplement, underlying smart contracts, articles of organization and operating agreement, if applicable, of a decentralized autonomous organization may define, reduce or eliminate fiduciary duties and may restrict transfer of ownership interests, withdrawal or resignation from the decentralized autonomous organization.

Participation in the AUTX protocol and any associated governance token is subject to the smart contract rules, articles of organization, and operating agreement of the Wyoming DAO LLC. Members should review all governing documents prior to participation.

11.1 Operation of New Mechanisms Within the Wyoming DAO LLC Framework

The shadow-listing discovery surface described in Section 2 operates within the protocol's existing publication and routing authority. Shadow listings do not create members of the DAO LLC. They create catalog entries that point to unaffiliated third-party services. Creating a shadow listing does not transfer any membership interest, does not create any token, and does not create any voting right. The cryptographic claim flow that may convert a shadow listing into a claimed agent triggers a deployment under `AgentFactory.sol`. The per-agent ERC-20 AgentToken issued upon claim operates under the same protocol rules, the same bonding curve mathematics, and the same fee schedule as native launches issued under the existing protocol. The shadow-listing surface is a scale expansion of the protocol's existing publication and routing function, not a new instrument or governance class.

The x402 facilitator settlement path described in Section 3 operates within the protocol's existing service-order metering function. The 10/72/18 split is the same split that applies to non-x402 service orders under the existing protocol. The x402 path adds a settlement primitive at the buyer-onramp layer; it does not modify the protocol's role as proxy and metering counterparty.

The `CreditVault.sol` stored-value primitive described in Section 4 operates as a USDC custody contract for the convenience of buyers prepaying for service credits. It does not create membership interests, does not create voting rights, and does not represent a claim on the protocol's revenue. Withdrawal is at the user's discretion at any time.

11.2 Howey Test Posture

The three-prong Howey analysis (SEC v. W.J. Howey Co., 328 U.S. 293 (1946)) stands reaffirmed with respect to each protocol primitive disclosed in this addendum:

1. **Investment of money.** Shadow listings pre-claim involve no investment of money. The discovery surface is free; the platform crawler generates the catalog entry without consideration from any party. The 302 redirect on any proxy request returns the user to the upstream endpoint without any value flowing to or from the protocol. The cryptographic claim flow is free: the developer signs an EOA message or completes a domain verification; no token is purchased, no consideration flows to the protocol, and the resulting AgentToken issues to the developer at zero protocol-side payment.

2. **Common enterprise.** Post-claim trading occurs against a per-agent ERC-20 AgentToken whose revenue stream tracks the USDC service fees paid for actual service consumption from that specific agent endpoint. Revenue does not pool across agents; each AgentToken's holders receive distributions only from the service revenue of the specific agent identified by that token. The mathematical reserve invariant $R(S) = k \cdot S^3 / 3$ documented in V1 §2 and V2 §2 binds per-curve. No centralized AUTX-driven enterprise pools token-holder fortunes. The protocol's role is metering and routing, not a managerial role over any specific agent's service operations.
3. **Expectation of profit derived from the efforts of others.** The per-agent revenue stream comes from service consumption purchased by buyers from the developer who operates the agent endpoint. The protocol provides metering, routing, and settlement infrastructure; it does not operate the agent's service. The economic value of any AgentToken comes from the unaffiliated developer's service operation and from buyer-side demand for that service, not from a managerial activity undertaken by the protocol on behalf of token holders.

The protocol therefore takes the position that the described primitives do not constitute investment contracts under the Howey framework. This document is a defensive prior-art disclosure. It is not a representation that any specific token has been registered or exempted from registration under any securities law, and it is not legal advice.

Part C: Freedom-to-Operate Posture

12. Status of Prior Claims and New Candidate Claims

12.1 Status of Prior Claims (V1 Claims A through D)

Claim A (reserve-integral cubic AMM, per-entity factory). Still novel in its full combination. No new prior art surfaced in the past 60 days. Verdict: keep, with the narrowed independent claim from `docs/PATENT_REVISION_PLAN.md` (permanent self-contained curve, fee-from-buyer-surplus solvency proof, decoupled service-revenue routing).

Claim B (SHA-256 output commitment for proxied AI inference). Still strongest. Zero prior art surfaced. Verdict: file provisional first; broaden independent claim to “cryptographic commitment scheme” with SHA-256 as a dependent fallback.

Claim C (UUID-scoped RFC 8693 token exchange). Still novel. No prior art surfaced. The audience-binding-to-logical-UUID pattern remains unique. Verdict: file provisional jointly with Claim B.

Claim D (DAO-governed ISO jurisdiction map with atomic legal-reserve extraction). Specified but `GovernanceGuard.sol` not yet deployed on Base mainnet. No new prior art. Verdict: defer provisional filing until the contract is deployed and exercising live transactions. Defensive disclosure remains in force.

12.2 Claim E. Claim-Gated Shadow Listing of Third-Party Service Catalogs

One-sentence summary. A method by which a marketplace operator autonomously crawls a third-party service catalog, generates collision-free auto-tickers from foreign service identifiers, creates non-tradable on-platform shadow listings that route consumers to the third-party endpoint, and atomically transitions any individual listing to tradable status only upon dual-path cryptographic claim by the originating service operator.

Patent-style claim language:

A computer-implemented method for incorporating third-party service catalog entries into a tokenized service marketplace, comprising:

- a. crawling, on a recurring interval, a public catalog endpoint of a third-party service registry, paginating across the registry's enumeration parameters to retrieve a complete record set;
- b. for each retrieved service record, deriving a collision-free auto-ticker by deterministic transformation of the foreign `service_id` field, where the transformation produces a fixed-prefix marketplace identifier and is verified against the marketplace's existing reserved and active ticker namespaces prior to insertion;
- c. inserting the service record into the marketplace database as a *shadow listing* in a non-tradable state, wherein the marketplace gateway responds to consumer requests against the shadow listing by issuing an HTTP 302 redirect to the foreign endpoint URL, and wherein the marketplace extracts no fee, mints no token, and operates no bonding curve against the shadow listing during the non-tradable state;
- d. reserving a configurable subset of brand-name tickers under generic substitute prefixes pending claim;
- e. publishing a public opt-out registry as a JSON manifest at a stable URL, wherein inclusion in the opt-out registry causes the next crawler cycle to remove or suppress any matching listing within a documented service-level takedown interval;
- f. accepting a claim by the original service operator via at least two distinct cryptographic proof paths, comprising:
 - g. a signature produced by the externally-owned account associated with the merchant settlement address declared in the third-party catalog entry, over a marketplace-issued challenge string; or
 - ii. a DNS TXT record published under the apex domain of the foreign endpoint URL containing a marketplace-issued challenge string;
- g. upon successful verification of either claim path, atomically transitioning the listing from non-tradable state to tradable state in a single database transaction, instantiating per-entity bonding curve, dividend splitter, and agent-token contracts, and binding ownership of all contract addresses to the claiming party's wallet;

wherein the autonomous publication step (c) is gated on a mainnet-only chain identifier so that listings cannot be auto-published to a non-production network; and

wherein the takedown service-level interval and opt-out registry are documented and externally callable independent of any owner claim.

Novel sub-elements vs prior art. 1. Dual-path claim (EOA signature OR DNS TXT) bound to the same atomic transition. Existing domain-verification systems (Google Search Console, ACME / Let's Encrypt) verify domain control but do not gate the activation of an on-chain bonding curve. Existing on-chain ENS / Basename ownership verification verifies wallet control but is not bound to a third-party catalog identifier. 2. Atomic transition from non-tradable shadow to tradable state in a single database transaction with concurrent contract instantiation. The non-tradable interim is a defined, documented state with zero fee extraction. 3. Public opt-out registry published as a stable-URL JSON manifest, externally callable, with a documented takedown SLA. No prior crawler-published catalog (Google Books, Internet Archive, Have I

Been Pwned) couples opt-out with on-chain primitive activation. 4. Brand-name reservation under generic substitute prefixes (SHDW. . .) prevents trademark conflict during the unclaimed interval. 5. Mainnet-only auto-publish gate is structural, not policy-enforced.

Enablement files. apps/api/app/services/shadow_crawler.py ;
apps/api/app/services/claim.py ; apps/api/app/services/trademark_guard.py ;
apps/api/app/services/ticker_reserved.py ; apps/api/alembic/versions/039_* through
042_* ; apps/web/src/app/opt-out.json/route.ts ;
apps/api/app/main.py::_shadow_crawler_job .

Closest prior art. - Domain Name System TXT-record verification (ACME RFC 8555). Verifies domain control; does not gate activation of a token market. - Google My Business unclaimed-listing model. Allows owner claim of crawled records but operates no on-chain primitive and no token issuance. - Pump.fun and Virtuals Protocol direct-launch flows. Require the originating party to launch the listing actively. Neither runs an autonomous catalog crawl with deferred dual-path claim. - Coinbase x402 reference catalog (x402.org/services). Read-only listing; no claim mechanism, no token activation.

12.3 Claim F. Reserve-First Three-Phase Atomic Service Launch

One-sentence summary. A method for tokenized service registration in which a database reservation is created and the chosen ticker is locked before any on-chain transaction is dispatched, such that an interrupted or rejected on-chain step does not produce a permanently-burned identifier without a corresponding off-chain record.

Patent-style claim language:

A computer-implemented method for atomic registration of a tokenized service entity, comprising:

- a. receiving from a client a reservation request specifying a candidate ticker and service metadata;
- b. executing all off-chain validation against the reservation request, including content moderation, ticker uniqueness across active and pending namespaces, payment verification, and field-level schema validation, prior to any blockchain interaction;
- c. inserting a database record in a `pending` state with the specified ticker locked in a uniqueness-enforced column, the record bearing a creation timestamp;
- d. returning to the client a reservation identifier and instructing the client to dispatch an on-chain factory call signed by an end-user-controlled wallet;
- e. accepting from the client an activation request bearing the reservation identifier, an on-chain transaction hash, and the deployer address;
- f. verifying the transaction receipt against the configured factory contract address, confirming the emitted launch event matches the reserved ticker and the originating account matches the declared deployer, and parsing the deployed per-entity contract addresses from the receipt;
- g. atomically promoting the database record to `active` state and persisting the parsed contract addresses, wherein the activation step is idempotent against re-submission of the same transaction hash;
- h. running a periodic cleanup job that releases any reservation older than a configurable time-to-live by transitioning the record to a terminal cancelled state and freeing the ticker;
- i. supporting a recovery path whereby the client persists the reservation identifier and the on-chain transaction hash to local browser storage at the moment of dispatch, such that a browser crash or session loss after dispatch but before activation can be resumed by reading local storage and re-issuing the activation request;

wherein the property is established that no ticker may be permanently bound on-chain by the factory contract without a corresponding reservation in the database.

Novel sub-elements. 1. The database-lock-before-chain ordering is the structural anti-burn property. Existing token launchpads accept on-chain launch transactions without prior database reservation. Identifier collisions or naming conflicts are resolved post-hoc on-chain. 2. Idempotent activation keyed on transaction hash, with strict factory-address and event-payload verification, defends against cross-contract replay. 3. Browser-crash recovery via dual-key local storage with explicit resume on next page load is documented as part of the protocol. 4. Time-to-live cleanup of pending reservations releases tickers without orphaning them.

Enablement files. `apps/api/app/routers/agents.py` ;
`apps/api/app/services/agent_launcher.py` ;
`apps/api/app/services/chain.py::verify_agent_launch` ;
`apps/web/src/app/launch/page.tsx` ; `apps/api/app/main.py` (TTL cleanup task);
`contracts/src/AgentFactory.sol` .

Closest prior art. - ENS domain registration (commit-reveal). Two-phase, but both phases are on-chain. No off-chain reservation lock and no local-storage continuation. - Pump.fun token creation. One-step on-chain mint; no reservation. - Virtuals agent launch. On-chain-first;

metadata is stored on-chain at launch.

12.4 Claim G. Bidirectional Catalog Manifest Bridge (Defensive Disclosure)

One-sentence summary. A method for protocol interoperability between two service catalogs in which the second catalog publishes a manifest at a stable URL whose JSON schema mirrors the first catalog's enumeration response, such that a consumer client speaking the first catalog's protocol may reach the second catalog by base-URL substitution alone.

Patent-style claim language. Reproduced in `apps/web/src/app/x402-services.json/route.ts` and at length in the synthesis draft. Counsel recommends defensive disclosure rather than provisional filing because the components individually fall within ordinary skill and the combination's commercial enforcement value is low. Defensive publication via this addendum prevents a third party (notably the reference catalog operator) from filing a patent that would foreclose the substitutability primitive.

12.5 Claim H. Diversified Synthetic Settlement Canary (Defensive Disclosure)

One-sentence summary. A method for continuous active monitoring of a payment-protocol settlement path in which a population of independently-funded externally-owned accounts and a population of platform-owned target services are rotated together against a randomized cadence weighted by clock hour, with mutual exclusion enforced via a distributed-lock-keyed next-fire timestamp.

Novel sub-elements. 1. Self-funding via routing canary spend back through the platform's own revenue split is a structural cost-reduction novelty. Conventional synthetic monitoring (Datadog, Pingdom, Coinbase's own monitoring) is pure cost. 2. Business-hours-weighted jitter coupled with distributed-lock-keyed next-fire timestamp decouples cadence from cron tick rate. 3. Diversification across both accounts and targets simultaneously, defending against detection by per-source or per-target filtering at the facilitator layer. 4. Pre-canary organic seeding (each canary EOA receives at least one non-canary transaction from its funding source before going live) reduces statistical clustering signatures.

Enablement files. `apps/api/app/services/x402_canary.py` ;
`apps/api/app/services/wallet_balance_monitor.py` ;
`scripts/spin_up_canary_agents.py` ; `docs/X402_DIVERSIFIED_CANARY_PROTOCOL.md` .

Counsel recommends defensive disclosure rather than provisional filing.

12.6 Claim I. Fail-Closed Treasury Solvency Pre-Check at Settlement Authorization

One-sentence summary. A method for runtime authorization of creator-revenue settlement in which an on-chain balance read against the platform's settlement signer is performed in the same request scope as the settlement-authorizing API call, returning a deny decision on any indeterminate chain-state response, and auto-tripping a platform-wide circuit breaker when the observed balance falls below a critical threshold.

Patent-style claim language:

A computer-implemented method for fail-closed solvency authorization of token-denominated revenue settlement, comprising:

- a. maintaining a settlement signer account whose responsibility is the dispatch of revenue-settlement transactions on behalf of platform-registered service operators;
- b. at each request to authorize a settlement transaction, executing within the request scope an on-chain balance query against the settlement signer for the specified settlement currency, and an on-chain balance query against the platform's custody contract;
- c. returning a deny decision and aborting the settlement authorization if the queried balance is insufficient to satisfy the requested settlement amount, *and additionally* returning a deny decision if either balance query returns an error, an indeterminate state, or a network-layer failure;
- d. operating a recurring out-of-band monitor at a configurable interval that records balance snapshots to a telemetry sink and, upon any snapshot in which the settlement signer balance falls below a configured critical threshold, atomically setting the platform's named circuit-breaker `platform` to an open state, wherein the open state of the `platform` breaker overrides all per-feature circuit breakers and causes the gateway to reject all revenue-impacting traffic;
- e. issuing an out-of-band notification to operations personnel concurrent with each auto-trip event;

wherein both the settle-side runtime guard of step (b)-(c) and the cron-side auto-trip of step (d) are independently engaged and either alone is sufficient to halt creator-revenue settlement on a balance-deficient signer.

Novel sub-elements. 1. Fail-closed semantics on indeterminate chain-state response, distinct from typical fail-open availability-favoring patterns. The protocol's content moderation similarly fails closed; the runtime treasury check extends this discipline to settlement. 2. Two-track architecture: per-request runtime guard plus periodic auto-trip cron, with explicit override semantics in which the platform-level breaker dominates per-feature breakers. 3. Atomic on-chain balance read inside the request scope of an off-chain authorization, with the read result determining the authorization outcome.

Enablement files. `apps/api/app/services/treasury_monitor.py` ;
`apps/api/app/services/circuit_breaker.py` ;
`apps/api/app/services/chain.py::usdc_balance_of` , `::platform_signer_address` ;
`apps/api/app/routers/agents.py::withdraw_earnings` ; `docs/TREASURY_RUNBOOK.md` .

Closest prior art. - General circuit-breaker pattern (Hystrix, Resilience4j). Software-only; no chain read. - DeFi solvency proofs (proof-of-reserves attestations). Periodic and external; not coupled to per-request authorization.

Counsel recommends provisional filing for Claim I.

13. Updated Filing Priority and Watchlist

13.1 Filing Priority

Priority	Claim	Action	Cost	Timeline
1	B + C combined	File provisional patent	\$320	This week
2	E (shadow listing dual-path claim)	File provisional patent	\$320	Within 14 days
3	F (reserve-first three-phase launch)	File provisional patent	\$320	Within 30 days
4	A (narrowed)	File provisional patent	\$320	Within 30 days
5	I (fail-closed treasury solvency)	File provisional patent	\$320	Within 60 days
6	D (DAO jurisdiction map)	Deploy GovernanceGuard.sol mainnet, then file	\$320	Within 90 days
Defensive only	G (catalog manifest bridge)	Disclosure in this V3; no provisional	\$0	This publication
Defensive only	H (diversified canary)	Disclosure in this V3; no provisional	\$0	This publication

Total provisional outlay across the next 90 days: \$1,920 (six provisionals at \$320 USPTO micro-entity rate).

13.2 Decision Points

If a competitor publishes a comparable shadow-listing crawler, accelerate Claim E to priority 1. If GovernanceGuard.sol deploys to Base mainnet within 30 days, accelerate Claim D ahead of Claim I. If x402 facilitator economics change such that the protocol considers offering canary-as-a-service to third parties, accelerate Claim H to provisional.

13.3 Prior-Art Watchlist Updates

Continue monitoring the V1 list (Virtuals Protocol, PathDAO, Jansen Teng, Wee Kee Tiew, generic “Base L2 AI agent marketplace” filings). Add the following new watch targets surfaced by the 2026-04 work:

- **Coinbase Developer Platform x402 BD team.** Coinbase has commercial incentive to enclose the x402 protocol surface. Watch for facilitator-side patent filings (settlement validation, EIP-3009 replay protection variants, merchant signer architectures); any patents naming Erik Reppel, Brett Winton, or x402 Foundation contributors; filings that touch synthetic-canary monitoring of payment protocols.
- **agentic.market team (operator and contributors).** The risk of a defensive patent on “third-party catalog enumeration as a service” or “service-id-to-ticker derivation” exists and would target Claim E directly. Identify the operating entity from WHOIS, GitHub org, and any LLC filings; watch USPTO PatentCenter and PCT publications under those names monthly.

- **Linux Foundation x402 Foundation.** Watch for any “x402 Foundation IP pledge” terms that would constrain freedom to operate on facilitator-adjacent inventions.
 - **Pump.fun (continued).** Watch for filings related to anti-sniping, reservation-based launches, or graduation-mechanic variants.
 - **OpenAI / Anthropic agent-platform filings.** Watch for filings on agent registration, credit metering, or session billing that could read on Claims F or I.
 - **Trademark watch on the AUTX wordmark.** Confirm USPTO trademark search shows no conflicting class-9 or class-42 registrations. File an Intent-to-Use trademark application before any major press cycle.
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14. References

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15. Version History

Version	Date	Summary
1.0.0	2026-03-08	Initial disclosure: Claims A, B, C, D. Reserve-integral bonding curve, ZK proxy with SHA-256 commitment and UUID-scoped RFC 8693, on-chain jurisdiction enforcement. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.18911878.
2.0.0	2026-04-01	Added: AXP (API key architecture, manifest, binary metering, webhooks, SSRF), receipt + replay protection, user-signed launch with on-chain receipt verification, named-feature platform circuit breaker, content moderation as structural gate, USDC denomination of bonding curve. Permanence property added to AMM. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.19376038.
3.0.0	2026-05-04	Added: shadow-listing architecture with two-path cryptographic claim (Claim E), x402 Phase E settlement architecture LIVE on Base mainnet, <code>CreditVault.sol</code> mainnet alpha deployment with role-separated access control, reserve-first three-phase service launch with anti-burn invariant (Claim F), bidirectional catalog manifest bridge (Claim G defensive), diversified synthetic settlement canary (Claim H defensive), fail-closed treasury solvency pre-check (Claim I). Updated regulatory analysis: third-party shadow listing compliance (Lanham, GDPR Article 6, notice-and-takedown analog), money transmission and stored-value posture, Wyoming DAO LLC scope confirmation, Howey Test re-analysis. Updated FTO posture and prior-art watchlist.

Submitted for defensive prior art publication. All described systems are deployed in the AUTX protocol codebase as of the filing date and are publicly observable on Base mainnet. This document is the new version of V2 (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.19376038, 2026-04-01) and the prior version V1 (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.18911878, 2026-03-08), with respect to mechanisms shipped between 2026-04-19 and 2026-05-03. Released under CC0 1.0 Universal (public domain dedication).